

1 **A PIECE OF THE ECOTOXICOLOGY PUZZLE: HOW CAN CURRENT AND FUTURE**
2 **RESEARCH INFORM PPD REGULATIONS?**

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48 **Abstract**

49 2-((4-Methylpentan-2-yl)amino)-5-(phenylamino)cyclohexa-2,5-diene-1,4-dione commonly
50 known as 6PPD-Quinone (6PPD-Q), is the ozonized derivative of, N-(1,3-dimethylbutyl)-N'-
51 phenyl-p-phenylenediamine, 6PPD. 6PPD is a common tire coating that prevents rubber
52 degradation by acting as an antioxidant. Research efforts elucidating 6PPD-Q's toxicity surged
53 after a 2021 study identified 6PPD-Q as an acute mortality inducing toxicant to coho salmon.
54 This commentary functions as a compilation of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q's interaction with aquatic and
55 terrestrial organisms. We also encompass studies providing toxicological explanations of
56 dysregulation of intracellular activity and metabolite transformation. We aim to concurrently
57 impart an overview of the most current 6PPD and 6PPD-Q studies at organismal and cellular
58 levels, emphasize research gaps, such as the lack of global regulations, and propose possible
59 routes for future studies, like the expansion into different model organisms, lifecycle effects,
60 fertility and transgenerational effects, and cancer cell studies.

61
62 **Introduction**

63 For years, freshwater environments have been experiencing "urban stream syndrome," a
64 phenomenon attributed to the increased environmental pollutants altering water quality.¹ In
65 urbanized areas, road runoff is a contributing factor to the decline in freshwater habitats. Pacific
66 salmon, more specifically coho salmon, are integral to the diverse connection between saltwater
67 and freshwater food webs.² However, coho salmon have been experiencing acute mortality
68 rates when migrating to freshwater ecosystems to reproduce. In 2021, N-(1,3-dimethylbutyl)-N'-
69 phenyl-p-phenylenediamine-quinone, 6PPD-Quinone (6PPD-Q), was identified as the main
70 contributor to the acute mortality rate seen in coho salmon.³ While this discovery is recent, its
71 precursor 6PPD, was originally discovered in the 1960s. 6PPD falls within a class of compounds
72 called p-phenylenediamine (PPD) which are used as antiozonant coatings on rubber tires to
73 prevent breakdown and prolong usage.⁴ Since then, there have been no alternative
74 antiozonants that match 6PPDs ability to prevent rubber breakdown.

75 As such, 6PPD has become a prominent environmental pollutant in recent years. When
76 entering the environment, 6PPD can react with ozone creating 6PPD-Quinone (6PPD-Q)
77 (Figure 2).⁵ Quinones, when introduced *in vivo*, can induce cytotoxicity, immunotoxicity, or
78 activate detoxification enzymes, depending on their reactivity.⁶ Both molecules are ubiquitous
79 and readily enter the environment through road run-off, rubber waste, and dust, accumulating in
80 both rural and urban waterways (Supplemental Figure 1 and Supplemental Table 1). The half-
81 life of 6PPD is approximately 5 hours in water compared to 6PPD-Q which has a half-life of
82 about 33 hours.⁷ Although the half-lives of both chemicals are relatively short, the amount of
83 tires on the road at any given time contribute to the continual leaching of PPDs into waterways.
84 Additionally, even small amounts of PPDs, in the ng/L range, can lead to mortality among
85 aquatic wildlife. This indicates high reactivity. Thus, continued usage of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q has
86 raised concern for aquatic life subjected to these chemicals.

87 Furthermore, coho salmon seem to be more sensitive to PPDs unlike other freshwater
88 species. The coho salmon mortality discovery has opened the door to a new field in
89 ecotoxicology research. More publications have revealed species, like zebrafish, with higher
90 tolerances to 6PPD and 6PPD-Q.⁷⁻¹⁸ Additionally, other species and *in vitro* models, when
91 exposed to PPDs, have exhibited metabolic changes and dysregulated genes.^{4,10,19-23} Studies

92 investigating PPD exposure in humans living in areas with high rubber recycling reported
93 similar changes to metabolism.^{19,20,24–26}

94 Though impacts of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q are widespread, there are no global regulations
95 against PPD usage. The United States Environmental Protection Agency, USEPA, is supplying
96 funding to expand the understanding of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q's impact and has developed an
97 action plan to mitigate the risks.^{27,28} The United States has completed initial aquatic life
98 screenings to discern the acute exposure levels for 6PPD and 6PPD-Q, 8.9 µg/L and 11 ng/L,
99 respectively.^{29,30} Comparatively, the Canadian Environmental Protection Agency, CEPA, has
100 added PPDs to their substance priority list and are working towards possibly implementing a
101 ban.³¹ The European Union's Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of
102 Chemicals, REACH, is also considering employing restrictions of 6PPD use.³² Whichever
103 country or region can amass sufficient research to support and implement their own regulations
104 will likely help direct other global regulations.

105 Although other 6PPD reviews and commentaries have been published covering
106 environmental impacts on individual species, our commentary aims to summarize what is known
107 thus far about the toxic effects of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q in multiple aquatic organisms, model
108 organisms, and human cell lines. To aid in comparison between species and cell lines,
109 conversions of environmental concentrations (µg/L) of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q to molar
110 concentrations are provided for reference (Supplemental Table 2). We aim to point out the gaps
111 occurring within the 6PPD and 6PPD-Q research domain and provide suggestions to drive
112 scientific discovery, understanding, and regulations. Our recommendations include,
113 transgenerational studies, toxicological impacts on female model organisms, epigenetics,
114 implementation of fungal models, fate of PPD metabolites, toxicity to cancer cells, single cell,
115 and co-exposure of environmental toxicants.

116
117 Figure 1. Timeline of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q development, implementation, and toxic nature
118 (created using [BioRender.com](https://www.biorender.com)).

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120
 121 Figure 2. Transformation of 6PPD to 6PPD-Q in the presence of ozone (O₃) (created using
 122 BioRender.com).
 123

124 **Methods**

125 To gather data, we used the National Library of Medicine (NIH) search engine PubMed.
 126 For example, we used keywords, 6PPD, 6PPD-Q, zebrafish, coho salmon, and *Caenorhabditis*
 127 *elegans* to identify how many papers had been published within this field of study. To further
 128 narrow our search, we included combinations of keywords into our searches such as “6PPD,
 129 zebrafish.” We then sorted through each paper to determine which area of study the paper
 130 focused on and if the information fit into the focus of our manuscript. We were unable to employ
 131 any time restrictions to our searches because all relevant research has been published within
 132 the last five years. Any paper published and available through PubMed was considered for our
 133 commentary.
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135 **Aquatic Organisms To what extent are coho salmon (*Oncorhynchus kisutch*)** 136 **affected by 6PPD-Q?**

137 Many efforts have been made to thoroughly investigate the consequences of
 138 environmental pollutant 6PPD-Q on coho salmon. Coho salmon are of high ecological
 139 importance because of well-documented “coho pre-spawn mortality” of adult coho salmon
 140 returning to spawn. A 2021 study was the first to evaluate mortality in coho salmon following
 141 recognition of the ecological phenomenon (Table 1). Researchers used juvenile coho salmon as
 142 a stand-in representative for adult coho salmon. 6PPD-Q was found to be highly toxic with the
 143 mean lethal concentration being $0.79 \pm 0.16 \mu\text{g/L}$ after only 2 to 6 hours of exposure.³ Following
 144 this report, efforts have been made to investigate toxicity at all coho salmon life stages. Coho
 145 salmon embryos have been tested for growth and survival effects following 6PPD-Q exposure.
 146 Multiple 6PPD-Q exposures found significant embryonic mortality observed at $7.22 \mu\text{g/L}$, as 79
 147 percent of treated embryos failed to hatch. In addition, 21 percent of the treated embryos
 148 exhibited significant adverse development and growth.⁵ In a different study, three week old
 149 juveniles had a median LC50 of 41.0 ng/L after 24 hours of constant exposure.³³ An adult study
 150 found acute mortality to be induced at a slightly higher concentration of 1.3 to $1.8 \mu\text{g/L}$ 6PPD-
 151 Q.³⁴ Taken altogether, these findings indicate that even within species, the tolerance level of
 152 6PPD-Q varies depending on life stage. This presents the need to continually implement the
 153 assessment of species’ progressional life stages into toxicology studies. Confirming lethal

154 concentrations for embryonic to adult populations will help inform regulations and preserve
155 sensitive species' populations.

156 157 **How does the mortality rate in zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) compare to coho salmon?**

158 Like coho salmon, zebrafish embryos and larvae are being used to investigate the
159 effects of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q because they are considered a “tolerant” species.¹⁶ Their short
160 gestational times and transparent bodies make morphological studies simple and accessible.
161 Several studies have expanded upon 6PPD-Q’s effect on coho salmon by testing environmental
162 levels of both PPD compounds on zebrafish. In three studies, treatment of 6PPD and its
163 quinone derivative induce various morphological transformations and mortality rates in zebrafish
164 (Table 1). Depending on the method of exposure and analysis, the lethal concentrations of
165 PPDs can vary. Using zebrafish embryos, one study maintained stable concentrations of 6PPD
166 and 6PPD-Q for 96 hours. They then estimated the lethal concentrations to be 442.62 µg/L and
167 132.92 µg/L respectively.⁸ When exposed to stable concentrations of 6PPD for 120 hours the
168 tolerance increased. This was confirmed using UPLC-QE. The measured LC50 was 0.87 mg/L
169 6PPD and no significant effect was found upon treatment of 6PPD-Q up to 10 mg/L.¹⁸ It is
170 important to note the aforementioned studies differ in experimental design, data acquisition, and
171 analysis making comparisons between LC50 values difficult. Compared to coho salmon the lack
172 of acute toxicity in zebrafish tends to label them as “tolerant,” however, since the LC50 values
173 vary so greatly depending on methodology, the definitive categorization of zebrafish may be
174 more nuanced.

175 176 **How do PPDs affect zebrafish morphology, behavior, and physiology?**

177 The reasoning for zebrafish’s classification as “tolerant,” extends beyond the lethal
178 concentration as PPDs also affect morphology, behavior, and physiology. Multiple studies have
179 observed morphological alterations. Variable 6PPD concentrations resulted in decreases in eye
180 development and eye size, hatchability, body length, and swim bladder size.^{8,10,13,14,18}
181 Comparatively, zebrafish exposed to a range of 6PPD-Q concentrations, had no significant
182 changes to bladder development. However, zebrafish had increased instances of reduced eye
183 size, lordosis, kyphosis, and malformations of the tail.^{8,14,18} While decrease in eye size is
184 consistent between both chemicals, other morphological effects indicate a difference in 6PPD
185 and 6PPD-Q’s biological targets.

186 Along with morphological changes, 6PPD also altered zebrafish behavior and
187 physiological conditions. After 96 hours of exposure to 25 µg/L 6PPD, zebrafish larvae
188 experienced a decrease in total swim distance, angular swim velocity and heart rate (BPM).
189 Zebrafish also experienced a dose-dependent increase in oxygen consumption.⁸ Likewise, a
190 different study discovered after 120 hours of exposure to 0.4 mg/L zebrafish larvae had inhibited
191 phototactic behavior.³⁵ Between these two studies, 6PPD caused altered behavior and
192 interfered with normal physiological processes. These alterations are likely closely associated
193 with the morphological abnormalities previously discussed.

194 Similarly, 6PPD-Q also induced altered behavior and interfered with physiological
195 processes. When exposed to 10 and 25 µg/L 6PPD-Q for 96 hours zebrafish exhibited
196 decreased total swim distance and angular swim velocity.⁸ A different study showcased the
197 same decrease in total swim distance using a higher concentration of 6PPD-Q, 50 µg/L, and an

198 extended exposure time of 120 hours.¹⁰ Additionally, a third study used low doses of 20, 200
199 ng/L, and 2000 ng/L over a 24 hour period and observed decreased locomotive activity and
200 increased sleeping bouts during daylight cycles.¹⁶ Taken together, both PPDs cause significant
201 morphological, behavioral, and physiological changes in zebrafish. Even “tolerant” species are
202 experiencing adverse symptoms when exposed to PPDs further exacerbating the need to
203 implement global regulations.

204

205 **How are Terrestrial Organisms affected by PPDs?**

206 **1. Mice (*Mus musculus*)**

207 Toxic effects of 6PPD-Q have also started to be studied in mammalian models such as
208 male mice. Male mice offer a good fertility model because of their short reproductive times.
209 Across many studies, 6PPD-Q has been found to complicate reproductive processes and
210 induce inflammation responses (Table 1).³⁶⁻⁴² In one study, when injected with 4 mg/kg 6PPD-
211 Q, mouse testosterone levels decreased and sperm quality declined. This led to complications
212 in *in vitro* fertilization (IVF) and suggests impaired male fertility.⁴¹ Additionally, pathways
213 involving spermatogenesis and sphingolipid metabolism were differentially affected.⁴¹

214 Furthermore, multiple studies observed fluctuations in inflammation responses. Two
215 studies employed different methods of 6PPD-Q exposure on two mouse models. The first
216 injected 10 and 100 µg/kg for 21 days and the second injected one dose of 4 mg/kg and
217 monitored response over one week. Both saw an increase in the inflammatory cytokines, TNF-
218 α, IL-1, IL-6, and IL-10.^{37,38} A third study injected mice with 0.4 and 4 mg/kg 6PPD-Q every 4
219 days for a 28-day period and saw similar increases in inflammatory cytokines. They also
220 discovered apoptosis, blood-brain barrier disruption, and increased levels of reactive oxygen
221 species (ROS).³⁹

222 6PPD-Q has also been found to contribute to hepatotoxicity in mice. Long term exposure
223 for 21 days via the oral route, (0.1 and 1 µg/kg bw per day) led to elevated lipid deposition in the
224 liver which can contribute to metabolic dysfunction-associated steatotic liver disease
225 (MASLD).⁴⁰ These selected mice studies highlight the various toxic effects of 6PPD-Q. There is
226 still a major research gap including female mice as well as exposure to 6PPD. Because of the
227 wide effects of 6PPD-Q, additional studies focusing on these areas would improve our
228 understanding of the toxic mechanisms of both PPDs allowing for better informed policy and
229 regulations.

230 **2. Humans (*Homo sapiens*)**

231 To better understand the effects of 6PPD and its quinone derivative on human health
232 populations, epidemiology studies were carried out in areas with high electronic and rubber
233 waste disposal. Specifically, in industrialized China, children from ages 2 to 7 underwent urine
234 analysis to detect PPDs and results were compared to a control group located farther from the
235 waste disposal site. The median levels of PPDs, 6PPD 0.073 and 6PPD-Q 2.34 ng/mL, were
236 higher for the group in closer proximity to the waste plant.²⁴ Dust samples from houses,
237 kindergartens, and road areas with high levels of rubber recycling were compared to a control
238 and for houses and kindergartens the concentration of 6PPD-Q was higher, 3.2 and 7.5 ng/g,
239 respectively.²⁶ The same study also investigated the presence of polybrominated diphenyl
240 ethers (PBDEs), polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), and heavy metal(loid)s, (Ni and Cu) in
241 kindergarten dust samples. These toxicants are thought to be further associated with a

242 decrease in body mass index (BMI), alteration of the gut microbiota, and more frequent illnesses
243 such as influenza in areas with high rubber recycling (Table 1).^{25,26} Ingestion of dust in toddlers,
244 approximately 3.48 ng/kg bw/d, was also tracked to indoor venues through paint and flooring
245 materials.¹⁹ Although the main focus this far has been on PPDs effects in children, one study
246 detected the toxicants in breastmilk and adult urine.²⁰ This raises concerns that these tire
247 pollutants may be passing from parent to child. Currently, there are no regulations for
248 acceptable daily intake (ADI) or tolerable daily intake (TDI) for 6PPD or 6PPD-Q. More studies
249 encompassing dust exposure, human excretions, co-exposure with other toxicants, and
250 transgenerational transmission will give greater insight on exposure level so tolerance can be
251 established.

252 3. *Caenorhabditis elegans* (*C. elegans*)

253 While 6PPD-Q is often confirmed to be in freshwater environments, it has also been
254 found in dirt and air samples. *Caenorhabditis elegans* (*C. elegans*) offer unique insight upon
255 6PPD-Q exposure as they are often terrestrial but can also be found in aquatic environments.
256 Investigating mortality in nematodes revealed only a 5 percent mortality rate when subjected to
257 100 µg/L 6PPD-Q (Table 1). It was noted that the mortality level was nowhere near complete
258 sample mortality but was still significant when compared to the control group.⁴³ Though mortality
259 is uncommon in *C. elegans*, three studies found 6PPD-Q exposure resulted in a decreased
260 lifespan.⁴⁴⁻⁴⁶

261 Like zebrafish, behavioral changes also appear in *C. elegans*. Two studies found
262 treatment of lower 6PPD-Q concentrations ranging from 0.1 to 10 µg/L resulted in decreased
263 and abnormal locomotion.⁴⁷ Decreased locomotion was hypothesized to be caused by the
264 neurodegeneration observed in D-type neurons following exposure to 10 µg/L 6PPD-Q.⁴⁸
265 Neurodegeneration was also observed in dopaminergic, glutamatergic, serotonergic, and
266 GABAergic neurons causing decreased sensory perception and neurotransmission.⁴⁷
267 Comparatively, exposure to 1 to 10 µg/L 6PPD-Q resulted in a decrease of dopamine synthesis
268 leading to a decrease of dopamine related behavior.⁴⁸ Therefore, 6PPD-Q seems to be a
269 neurotoxin, targeting a multitude of neurons and inhibiting normal behavior.

270 No morphological changes were indicated in any *C. elegans* studies; however, metabolic
271 and inflammatory responses were prevalent. Increased intestinal permeability was found in
272 nematodes exposed to 1 to 10 µg/L 6-PPD-Q.^{43,49} Metabolism appears to be broadly affected as
273 an increase in fatty acid synthesis resulted in lipid accumulation. Glycogen and glucose
274 metabolism were also inversely affected as 6PPD-Q exposure resulted in an increase of
275 glycogen metabolism and a decrease of glucose metabolism.⁵⁰⁻⁵³ Each of these responses
276 across multiple studies indicates the widespread toxic effects of 6PPD-Q. Moving forward,
277 continuing to study metabolic changes in *C. elegans* will lead to a better understanding of
278 6PPD-Q's biological targets and allow for better informed regulations.

279
280 Table 1. Summary of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q effect on aquatic organisms, terrestrial organisms, and
281 humans. High effect level indicates mortality at concentrations <100 µg/L 6PPD or 6PPD-Q with
282 severe deformities, and organ dysfunction. Moderate effect level indicates mortality induced at
283 concentrations ≥100 µg/L 6PPD or 6PPD-Q, and/or physiological and behavioral impairment.
284 Low effect level indicates mild or nonlethal effects, and/or limited biological impacts.

285 *Differences in LC50 values are likely due to differences in experimental design.

	Chemical treated	LC50	Effect Level	Biological Effects	Findings	References
Coho Salmon	6PPD-Q	Embryonic 7.22 µg/L Juvenile* 0.79 µg/L, 41.0 ng/L, 95 ng/L Adult 100 mg/L	High	Mortality, morphological, physiological	Decreased size, increased hematocrit	[^{3,5,33,34}]
Zebra fish	6PPD and 6PPD-Q	96 hr LC50 6PPD-Q of 132.92 µg/L, 96 hr LC50 6PPD of 442.62 µg/L and 2.2 mg/L, 120 hr IC50 6PPD of 0.87 mg/L*	Moderate	Mortality, morphological, physiological	Decreased eye size, hatchability, body length and swim bladder, decreased swimming and phototactic response, increased sleeping, altered heart rate, cardiac output, oxygen consumption, and hormone and neurotransmitters	[^{8,10,13,14,16,18}]
Brook Trout	6PPD-Q	Fry = 0.2 µg/L Fingerlings = 0.5 mg/L	High	Acute mortality, physiological	Increased interlamellar cell mass (ILCM) size, hematocrit, blood glucose, and total CO ₂ . Decreased blood sodium and chloride concentration	[⁵⁴]
Rainbow Trout	6PPD-Q	1.00 µg/L and 2.08 µg/L*	High	Acute mortality, physiological	Increased cardiorespiration, respiration, and metabolism	[^{55,56}]
Arctic Char	6PPD-Q	N/A	Low	Physiological	Increased metabolism	[⁵⁵]
Lake Trout	6PPD-Q	96 hr = 0.50 µg/L	High	Acute mortality, morphological	Caudal fin and eye deformities	[⁵⁷]

Mice	6PPD and 6PPD-Q	N/A	Moderate	Physiological	Decreased testosterone, sperm quality, altered spermatogenesis, and sphingolipid metabolism pathways. Increased inflammation and lipid accumulation	[37–41]
Humans	6PPD and 6PPD-Q	N/A	Moderate	Physiological	Decreased BMI, altered gut microbiome, and increased susceptibility to illnesses	[19,20,24–26]
C. Elegans	6PPD-Q	100 µg/L	Moderate	Moderate lethality, behavioral, physiological	Altered locomotion, increased intestinal permeability, neurodegeneration, lipid accumulation and glycogen metabolism. Decreased glucose metabolism and dopamine synthesis	[43–53,58]

286

287 **What is known about the metabolic fate of PPDs and their interactions with**
288 **proteins?**

289 The metabolic fate of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q is still largely unknown. PPDs have been
290 studied in *in vivo* and *in vitro* models including zebrafish, mice, human and rat liver microsomes,
291 rainbow trout liver cells (RTL-W1), and human liver cell lines (L02 and HepG2).^{7,12,21–23,59} A short
292 half-life of a toxicant showcases the need to identify potential biomarkers in the transformation
293 products (TPs). For example, in mice, the half-life of 6PPD-Q in blood, urine, and feces were
294 identified to be 5.32, 6.20, and 3.87 hours respectively.²³ When studying transformation
295 products of toxicants, typically transformations are labeled as Phase I and Phase II metabolites
296 with subsequent modifications. Across species, the TPs may vary depending on the metabolic
297 pathways used to detoxify 6PPD and 6PPD-Q. Two transformations of 6PPD-Q, hydroxylation
298 and glucuronidation, have been identified across species as common metabolites.^{7,12,21,23,59,60}
299 Likewise, the most common transformation of 6PPD is hydroxylation.⁷ Thorough research has
300 indicated strong potential for hydroxylation and glucuronidation TPs to act as effective
301 biomarkers for 6PPD-Q exposure, further investigation is needed to identify possible biomarkers
302 for 6PPD's metabolism.

303 Several studies have identified cytochrome p450 enzymes, CYP1A, CYP3A, 3A4, and
304 2C19, as integral to the metabolic breakdown of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q.^{21,22,61} When CYP1A was
305 inhibited by α -naphthoflavone (ANF) and quercetin, the levels of unmetabolized 6PPD-Q
306 increased, indicating its enzymatic activity is imperative.²² Beyond interacting with metabolic
307 enzymes, PPDs also interact with proteins affiliated with blood, neurons, and cancer. Molecular
308 docking has confirmed 6PPD and 6PPD-Q forms complexes with human serum albumin (HSA),
309 alters the secondary structure, and differentially affects the esterase activity.⁶² 6PPD-Q has also
310 been shown to interact with neuronal proteins involved in neurotransmitter reception and
311 synthesis, for example BAS-1, GLB-10, and acetylcholinesterase.^{47,48,63} These interactions are
312 likely the basis for the neurotoxicity seen in the presence of 6PPD-Q. Molecular docking has
313 also uncovered 6PPD-Q's potential effect on prostate cancer signaling pathway proteins.
314 Normally, JAK2 is involved in regulating the cell cycle, but since it has strong binding affinity
315 with 6PPD-Q, this has implications regarding the metastasis of prostate cancer.⁶⁴ Taken
316 together, the metabolic breakdown and widespread protein interactions of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q
317 complicate our full understanding of their toxicological implications. We believe not addressing
318 these complications may prevent progress in policy making. As stated, solidifying metabolic
319 biomarkers for both PPDs is the first step towards understanding how these toxicants interact *in*
320 *vivo* and *in vitro*.

321

322 **How do PPDs affect gene regulation prior to the inflammatory response?**

323 Current research indicates a trend in 6PPD and 6PPD-Q's proclivity to prompt an
324 organism's immune response, primarily via the organism's inflammation pathway.
325 We aim to distinguish differences in an organism's gene regulation seen leading up to, during,
326 and after the inflammatory response.

327 Prior to inducing an inflammatory response, PPDs create a stressful environment that
328 results in cellular oxidative damage. This is characterized by an elevation of ROS levels. Many
329 studies directly measured ROS levels following 6PPD treatment and found an increase in ROS
330 in embryonic, larval, and adult zebrafish.^{11,12,65-68} In comparison, 6PPD-Q was found to induce
331 oxidative stress within human liver cell lines like L02 and HepG2 as well as in *C. elegans* and
332 mice.^{22,38,42,48,69,70}

333 To further confirm the presence of increased ROS following PPD treatment, researchers
334 have analyzed the regulation of antioxidant genes responsible for mediating oxidative stress like
335 SOD-2, SOD-3, and SOD-4. Two studies found increased expression of antioxidant genes,
336 further indicating oxidative stress is caused by PPDs.^{42,63} *C. elegans*, tend to employ the
337 mitochondrial unfolded protein response (mt UPR) in the presence of oxidative stress.
338 Specifically, this response is mediated by set-6, met-2, jmjd-1.2, and jmjd-3.1. These genes
339 were dysregulated in the presence of 6PPD-Q, thereby hindering the mt UPR response and
340 increasing *C. elegans*' susceptibility to oxidative damage.^{71,72} Consistent exposure to PPDs may
341 prolong the stressful cellular conditions causing continued ROS production. ROS then act as
342 signaling molecules launching an inflammation response.⁷³

343

344 **How do PPDs affect gene regulation of the inflammatory response?**

345 After consistent PPD exposure elevates ROS, an inflammatory response is generated by
 346 the upregulation of proinflammatory genes. These genes code for cytokines which activate the
 347 immune response and participate in their own positive feedback mechanism.^{72,74}

348 Studies have looked at gene dysregulation of cytokines following 6PPD exposure in
 349 mice, zebrafish, and human lung and endometrial epithelial cells.^{36,66,75,76} An upregulation of
 350 TNF α confirmed 6PPD causes propagation of the NF- κ B and MAPK inflammation pathways was
 351 found. Studies also analyzed gene dysregulation of cytokines following 6PPD-Q exposure in
 352 coho salmon, mice, and humans.^{5,37,38,66} A more comprehensive list of dysregulated cytokines
 353 and inflammatory pathways were amassed. Similar to organisms treated with 6PPD, 6PPD-Q
 354 also caused an upregulation of cytokine TNF α again confirming activation of the NF- κ B and
 355 MAPK pathways. Upregulated expression of other cytokines like IL-6, Ripk1, and Fadd indicate
 356 JAK-STAT, necrosis, and apoptosis are also prompted. Furthermore, cytokines' ability to create
 357 a positive feedback loop may induce chronic inflammation. This has been shown to further
 358 disrupt genes regulating metabolism of macromolecules.

359

360 **How do PPDs affect gene regulation following the inflammatory response?**

361 6PPD exposure has been well documented to dysregulate lipid metabolism in zebrafish.
 362 Multiple studies find an increased expression of genes regulating fatty acid synthesis like ppar γ
 363 and fasn-1, while there was a decreased expression of genes regulating β -oxidation like acs-2
 364 and ech-2.^{60,76-78} Dysregulation of lipid metabolism was further evidenced by an increase in
 365 triglyceride and cholesterol levels. In studies treating zebrafish and *C. elegans* with 6PPD-Q,
 366 upregulated lipid synthesis and downregulated β -oxidation were also prevalent.^{15,50}

367 Though there is evidence of other biomolecules, like glucose, with disrupted metabolism,
 368 lipids have been by far the most studied.⁶¹ Consequences may extend beyond gene
 369 dysregulation of lipids following continued PPD exposure. As mentioned before, following three
 370 weeks of 6PPD-Q exposure, mice displayed disrupted lipid metabolism which culminated in fatty
 371 liver disease.⁴⁰ For aquatic organisms known to experience long term exposure of the tire
 372 pollutants, this raises a serious risk of hepatotoxicity. Long term damage to the liver may further
 373 exacerbate the inflammatory response already prompted by the cellular stress of PPDs.

374

375

376 Table 2. Gene and protein dysregulation in coho salmon, zebrafish, mice, *C. elegans*, and
 377 endometrial epithelial cells and their morphological effects.

	Chemical treated	Genes and proteins dysregulated	Alterations to
Coho Salmon	0.1-7.2 μ g/L 6PPD-Q	TNF α , il1 β , JAM, and ifny	Blood brain barrier, vascular permeability, and inflammation
Zebrafish	2.2 mg/L 6PPD and 0.25-25 μ g/L 6PPD-Q	<i>rpe65a</i> , <i>opn1lw1</i> , <i>per1a</i> , <i>per3</i> , and <i>cry3a</i>	Thyroid signaling pathway, eye development, estrogen signaling and circadian rhythm
Mice	10-100 mg/kg 6PPD and 6PPD-Q	Ripk1, Fadd, Il-6st, and Il-16	Immune system, macrophage infiltration, and prostate cancer activation

Endometrial epithelial cells	1-10 μM 6PPD and 1 μM 6PPD-Q	TNF α , IL6, and TGF β 1	Endometrial receptivity and inflammatory responses
C. elegans	10 $\mu\text{g/L}$ 6PPD-Q	atfs-1, ubl-5, dve-1, fasn-1, and pod-2	Mitochondrial unfolded protein response and lipid accumulation

378
379 Figure 3. Comprehensive overview of known interactions of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q (created using
380 BioRender.com).

381
382 **Conclusion**

383 **Future Trends in PPD Research**

384 Through this literature search we aimed to summarize the toxicological effects of PPDs,
385 6PPD and 6PPD-Q, on aquatic and terrestrial organisms and point out the major gaps that need
386 to be addressed as regulations are developed. After compiling data covering *in vivo* and *in vitro*
387 models, it is clear that 6PPD and 6PPD-Q have some overlapping toxic effects but also some
388 distinct characteristics. Because the discovery of PPDs as an environmental toxicant is
389 relatively new, integrating interdisciplinary research methods will help increase knowledge and
390 help inform global regulations. We specifically recommend focusing on discerning the toxic
391 mechanisms of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q through the following routes:

- 392
- 393 **1. Transgenerational studies.** As seen with coho salmon, the tolerance level, although
394 small, increased throughout the lifecycle. Determining lifecycle tolerance differences for
395 robust species, sensitive species, and any in between will help environmentalists be well
396 informed when implementing PPD regulations for various habitats.
 - 397 **2. Female model organisms.** 6PPD and 6PPD-Q have been identified to disrupt
398 reproductive health in mice. The main focus has been on male mice and
spermatogenesis. This discovery is pertinent, however investigating the effects of PPDs

399 on female reproductive health is of equal importance. Additionally, any discoveries
400 associated with reproductive health may also be linked to transgenerational effects.

401 **3. Epigenetics.** Another route to address transgenerational research gaps is epigenetic
402 studies. This field gives insight into gene alterations at the individual level as well as
403 possible explanations for inheritance of mutations and exposure impacts.

404 **4. Fungal cell toxicology and metagenomics.** . Fungi are an integral aspect of water
405 ecosystems. Fungal communities give vital information about the health of the
406 ecosystem they reside in. No studies have ventured into the effects of PPDs on fungal
407 cells. This could be an interesting approach to discern effects of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q. As
408 fungal cells are single-celled eukaryotes, cell trafficking and protein interactions can
409 easily be studied. Implementation of yeast studies opens the door to faster turnaround of
410 data acquisition as well as multi-faceted research approaches, such as metabolomics,
411 metagenomics, transcriptomics, and bioaccumulation.

412 **5. Fate of metabolites and their interactions *in vivo*.** A preliminary foundation of 6PPD
413 and 6PPD-Q metabolites has been formed. Taking the available information and
414 continually building upon the metabolic fate and toxicity of PPD transformation products
415 is essential to determining exposure biomarkers. Ultimately, uncovering the general
416 pathways used to metabolize 6PPD and 6PPD-Q will aid in our understanding of their
417 mechanistic impact.

418 **6. PPD effects on cancer cell lines.** Using cancer cells as a model system is
419 advantageous because of the ease of culturing and wide availability. Since cancerous
420 cell lines are immortalized, making long term studies investigating toxicological effects
421 possible. Additionally, cancer cells offer great insight to processes such as programmed
422 cell death, viability and oxidative stress. These assessments are essential to uncovering
423 the mechanisms behind PPD toxicity and serve as a good model to investigate
424 remediation effects of different chemicals.

425 **7. Single-cell sequencing (SCS).** We discussed various studies using different model
426 organisms and cell lines showing toxic effects of PPDs. However, effects on different
427 organs have yet to be investigated. Single-cell sequencing will remedy this by giving
428 insight into how different cells react to 6PPD and 6PPD-Q exposure. This methodology
429 can be used to illustrate the potential toxicological effects across organ systems. As
430 6PPD and 6PPD-Q research progresses, single-cell sequencing should be one of the
431 next steps.

432 **8. Co-exposure of environmental toxicants.** 6PPD and 6PPD-Q are not isolated
433 toxicants. The likelihood of multiple toxic chemicals, like PHAs and metalloids,
434 interacting is high. Investigating co-exposure in as many model organisms as possible
435 would give insightful information on how different toxicants interact synergistically,

437
438 Figure 4. Summary of future trends in 6PPD and 6PPD-Q studies (created using
439 BioRender.com).
440

441 All the above-mentioned future research trends are equally important in advancing
442 scientific understanding of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q. Collectively, each area of emphasis will bridge
443 the gaps in knowledge and provide a more thorough understanding of tire pollutant impacts.
444 Eventually, this ground-breaking research will help formulate regulations and combat the toxic
445 effects of PPDs.
446

447 **Author Contributions**

448 E.B.: writing-original draft preparation, review, editing; M.M.: writing-original draft preparation,
449 review, editing; K.K.: review, editing, and supervision. All authors have read and agreed to the
450 published version of the manuscript.
451

452 **Funding statement**

453 This work was supported by Missouri State University's thesis funds to Emma Braun and Roy
454 Blunt Endowed Professorship funds to Kyoungtae Kim.
455

456 **Disclosure of interest**

457 The authors report there are no competing interests to declare.
458

459 **Data Availability Statement**

460 Data sharing is not applicable as no new data was created or analyzed in this review.
461

462 **Acknowledgements**

463 We thank Missouri State University for funding and technology usage. We are grateful to the
464 Kim lab members and faculty at Missouri State University for their insight and support. Lastly,

465 we thank Kyoungtae Kim for his guidance during the writing process. Writing this review would
466 not have been possible without his expertise.

467

468 **Abbreviations**

469 6PPD: (N-(1,3-dimethylbutyl)-N'-phenyl-p-phenylenediamine)

470 6PPD-Q: N-(1,3-dimethylbutyl)-N'-phenyl-p-phenylenediamine-quinone

471 USEPA: United States Environmental Protection agency

472 PPD: p-Phenylenediamine

473 CEPA: Canadian Environmental Protection Agency

474 REACH: Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals

475 NIH: National Institute of Health

476 LC50: Lethal concentration 50

477 UPLC-QE: Ultra performance liquid chromatography - Q Exactive Focus Orbitrap mass
478 spectrometry

479 BPM: beats per minute

480 IVF: *in vitro* fertilization

481 TNF α : Tumor Necrosis Factor - α

482 IL-1: Interleukin-1

483 IL-10: Interleukin-10

484 IL-6: Interleukin-6

485 *Il1b*: interleukin 1 *b* gene

486 *per1a*: Period circadian clock 1 a gene

487 *per3*: period circadian regulator 3

488 *cry3a*: cryptochrome circadian regulator 3a

489 Ripk1: Receptor-interacting serine/threonine-protein kinase 1

490 Fadd: Fas-associated death domain

491 Il-6st: Interleukin 6 Cytokine Family Signal Transducer

492 Il-16: Interleukin-16

493 SOD-2: superoxide dismutase 2 gene

494 SOD-3: superoxide dismutase 3 gene
495 SOD-4: superoxide dismutase 4 gene
496 ROS: Reactive oxygen species
497 MASLD: metabolic dysfunction-associated steatotic liver disease
498 BMI: Body mass index
499 PBDE: polybrominated diphenyl ethers
500 PCB: polychlorinated biphenyls
501 Ni: Nickel
502 Cu: Copper
503 ADI: acceptable daily intake
504 TDI: tolerable daily intake
505 ILCM: interlamellar cell mass
506 L02: human liver hepatocyte
507 HepG2: Hepatocellular carcinoma
508 TP: transformation product
509 Mt UPR: mitochondrial unfold protein response
510 *atfs-1*: Activating Transcription Factor associated with Stress-1
511 *ubl-5*: ubiquitin-like protein 5
512 *dve-1*: homeobox transcriptional regulator
513 *fasn-1*: Fatty acid synthase 1 gene
514 *pod-2*: Acetyl-CoA Carboxylase gene
515 p450: cytochrome p450 protein
516 CYP1A2: Cytochrome p450 1A2
517 CYP3A: Cytochrome p450 3A
518 2C19: Cytochrome p450 2C19
519 ANF: α -naphthoflavone
520 BAS-1: cytochrome p450 superfamily protein

521 GRB-10: globin like protein 10
522 JAK2: Janus kinase 2
523 SOD: superoxide dismutase
524 HSA: Human Serum Albumin
525 NF- κ B: Nuclear factor kappa-light-chain-enhancer of activated B cells
526 PAH: polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons

527
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927
 928 Supplemental Figure 1. World map detailing locations that have detected 6PPD and 6PPD-Q
 929 (created using Biorender.com).

930
 931 Supplemental Table 1. Countries with 6PPD and/or 6PPD-Q detected in local samples.

Country	Location of Sample Site	Chemical	References
Argentina	Buenos Aires	6PPD-Q	[79]
Australia	Queensland (Brisbane River)	6PPD-Q	[80,81]
Brazil	São Paulo	6PPD-Q	[79]
Canada	Southern Ontario (Don River and Highland Creek) and Toronto	6PPD-Q	[79,82–84]
Chile	Santiago	6PPD-Q	[79]
China	Guangzhou (Liuxi River and Guanghua Basin), South China (Greater Bay Area), Guangdong (Pearl River and Dongjiang river), Zhejiang (Zhujiang river and Jiaojiang River), Yangtze River, Taiyuan, Zhengzhou, Shanghai, Nanjing, Hangzhou, and Hong Kong	6PPD and 6PPD-Q	[19,85–97]

Colombia	Bogota	6PPD-Q	[⁷⁹]
Germany	Leipzig Saxony	6PPD and 6PPD-Q	[⁹⁸⁻¹⁰¹]
India	Kolkata and New Delhi	6PPD-Q	[⁷⁹]
Japan	Tokyo	6PPD-Q	[^{79,102}]
Nigeria	Lagos	6PPD-Q	[⁷⁹]
Poland	Warsaw	6PPD-Q	[⁷⁹]
Spain	Madrid	6PPD-Q	[⁷⁹]
USA	California (San Francisco Bay), Colorado, Georgia, Kansas, Michigan, Minnesota, Mississippi (Oxford), New York, North Carolina, Oklahoma, Oregon, Texas, Virginia, and Washington (Tacoma)	6PPD-Q	[¹⁰³⁻¹⁰⁷]

932 Supplemental Table 2. Common concentrations of 6PPD* and 6PPD-Q* listed as micrograms
933 per liter (µg/L) and corresponding conversion to nanomolar (nM).

6PPD (µg/L)	6PPD (nM)	6PPD-Q (µg/L)	6PPD-Q (nM)
0.1	0.370	0.1	0.340
5	1.86	5	1.68
10	3.73	10	3.35
50	18.6	50	16.8
100	37.3	100	33.5
500	186	500	167.6
1000	373	1000	335

934 *Based on molar masses 6PPD, 268.4 g/mol and 6PPD-Q, 298.4 g/mol
935